

Potential Role Of Sports In Developing Self-Confidence As A Basic Psychological Skills

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 08, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: February 10, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Sports, Self-confidence, Psychological Skills, University, Students Athletes</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7626468</p>	<p><i>This research study was initiated to assess the potential role of sports in the development of self-confidence as a basic psychological skill. The population of the study involved seventeen (17) public sector universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (Kp) Pakistan. Two hundred and twenty-six (226), both male (n=144) and female (n=82) student-athletes, were selected as samples by using the available sampling procedure. A questionnaire (self-made) associated with said psychological perspective was developed by the researcher and used for collecting the required data from the respondents. The data gathered through the questionnaire were processed through a statistical package for social sciences (SPSS, version 24). The demographic attributes of respondents were calculated through percentage and frequency. Similarly, the study's hypotheses were tested using relevant statistical testing tools, i.e. correlation, regression, and test of significance etc. Based on the analysis, the researcher concluded that sports play a potential role in developing self-confidence as an essential psychological skill.</i></p>

Introduction

Sports are considered a type of exercise that may help us keep a healthy physique and a happy attitude which reflects positive behaviour (Green & Benjamin, 2009). Sports involve those physical activities which need proper timing, instrumentation, abilities, rules and regulations. Sport is taken to as an event in which individuals or teams compete against each other for fun and amusement, requiring physical energy and the ability to play. Sports play the role of an excellent tool for promoting the social life of individuals. Involvement in sporting events, on the one side, develops or promotes physique, and on the second side, it promotes the social traits among its participants (Gagne M, 2003, Khan et al., 2017).

Sports and physical activities develop the growing quality of children, such as coordination, strength and fitness. They also help children understand age-appropriate ideas about how their bodies move or become able to perform effective movements (Women's Sports Foundation, 2002).

Activism in sports during young age boosts health by making you healthy physically, mentally, emotionally and spiritually (Duda, 1989). Sporting events improve youth's quality of life and simultaneously enhance the development of personal and social skills that prepare children for adulthood (Gardner, 2002).

Socialization is the process of sharing activities in a society. The social person can not only be respected by the community concerned but is always on the leading front of society as an active member of society. Sports participation enables the athlete to act according to the need of the time and according to the situation by having an excellent emotional state of body (Khan, 2014).

Self-confidence is an inner assurance and can be found in many aspects of life. It is related to the mental and emotional constancy of a person. To develop self-confidence, one needs to participate in sports activities (Hays, Maynard & Bawden, 2009).

As we know, confidence plays an excellent role in the success and failure of a person. It means that confidence is a powerful tool for developing and improving athletic performance (Levy, 2010). Different psychological factors, i.e. anxiety, arousal, stress etc., affect performance. Participation in competitive sports reduces Anxiety, Arousal, Tension among the athlete developing self-confidence and self-esteem (Holt et al., 2017, Khan A & Khan S, 2014).

Both Self-confidence and Self-esteem help the athlete to prepare themselves for the activity. Adopting efficient coping strategies for competitive anxiety helps an athlete to control and manage all types of stressful situations accordingly (Hays, Maynard & Bawden, 2009, Khan et al., 2019, Khan et al., 2011).

According to Beth Rifkin (2015), one can improve self-confidence by adopting the following steps:

1. Study the situation and ask yourself about the approach that either you can do or not.
2. Improve your abilities and capabilities.
3. Practice a few times the activity which you want to do.
4. Make imagination about the success of the action.

5. Commit to yourself that you will train in all types of situations.

Self-confidence is by itself a tremendous success. It adversely affects the performance of an individual when it is lacking. A player with confidence in their performance always shows their worth during the competition. Most players fail to achieve their targets because they lose their confidence during the match (Bum et al., 2016).

The world of sports acknowledges the value of confidence, and success is directly proportional to confidence. Contestants are continuously assessed on their confidence level in their abilities to perform. Coaches, fans, and the media constantly discuss beliefs when speaking about the ability to win. Confidence can affect performance when our efficacy expectation is vital, and our capabilities are developed and promoted (Vealey & Chase, 2008).

Self-imagination and self-confidence in sports are well-known factors in increasing or improving athletic performance. Both self-imagination and self-confidence are vital in promoting sports or athletic performance (Hossein, 2012). In light of the above critical analysis of the literature, the following hypotheses were formulated and tested using appropriate statistical tools.

- There is a significant role of demographic attributes in sports participation and student-athletes self-confidence.
- There is a significant relationship between sports participation and the self-confidence of student-athletes.

Methods & Materials

The researcher adopted the following procedures to reach specific findings and conclusions; Population of the study involved seventeen (17) public sector universities of *Khyber Pakhtunkhwa* (Kp) Pakistan. There are eighteen hundred fifty-eight (1858) student-athletes in various Public Sector Universities of KP, Pakistan. Two hundred and twenty-six (226), both male (n=144) and female (n=82) student-athletes, were selected as samples by using the available sampling procedure. A questionnaire (self-made) associated with said psychological perspective was developed by the researcher and used for collecting the required data from the respondents. The researcher tested the instruments (SPQ) on a small scale before applying them on a large scale to find the difficulties, ambiguities and gaps within the questionnaire for a particular population. For pilot testing, the researcher took 30 respondents from the people (who did not entertain further in the actual study). The first draft of SPQ was distributed to the respondents and collected back after filling out the questionnaires. The researcher removed, modified and changed the statements of the questionnaires according to the pilot testing results. The piloted instrument was placed before sports sciences and physical education experts for content and facility. The researcher incorporated all the suggestions/corrections/changes obtained from the experts. The final draft of the instruments was used for reliability. The questionnaire was preceded through co-efficient alpha on the whole scale in estimating the internal consistency reliability. The reliability statistics for SPQ were found as .890. The data gathered through the questionnaire were processed through a statistical package for social sciences (SPSS, version 24). The demographic attributes of respondents were calculated through percentage and frequency. Similarly, the hypotheses of the study were tested through the use of relevant statistical testing tools, i.e. correlation, regression, and test of significance etc.

PRESENTATION OF DATA

Gender Wise differences on Sports Participation, and Self-confidence

Gender wise							
Variables	Gender	N	Mean	Std.	T	Df	Sig
Sport Participation	Male	144	2.6001	.41206	.600	224	.000
	Female	82	2.5693	2.6097			
Variables							
Self Confidence	Male	144	2.6097	.42744	.570	224	.000
	Female	82	2.5793	.29927			

The table above indicates differences based on gender regarding self-confidence and sports participation. Data were expressed through means, standard deviation, t-score and df. The total number of respondents was 226. Data about sports participation was shown as 2.60 +.412, t score was .600, df was 224 and P value was .000. Data about self-confidence shown as 2.60+2.60, t score was .570, df was 224 and P value was .000. The statistical inferences indicated that the p-values for all variables are lesser than the required critical threshold limit ($p > .05$). Therefore, hypothesis 5 is rejected.

Format of Sport-wise differences of Sports Participation, Self-confidence and Self-esteem

Format of Sport wise

Variables	Format of Sport	N	Mean	Std.	T	Df	Sig
Sport Participation	Individual	138	2.5701	.33956	-.956	224	.003
	Team	88	2.6185	.41644			
Variables							
Self Confidence	Individual	138	2.5891	.35632	-.465	224	.030
	Team	88	2.6136	.42889			

The table above indicates differences based on format-wise sports regarding self-confidence and sports participation. Data were expressed through means, standard deviation, t-score and df. The total number of respondents was 226. Data about sports participation was shown as 2.570+.339, t score was -.956, df was 224 and P value was .003. Data about self-confidence is shown as 2.58+.356, t score was -.465, df was 224 and P value was .030. However, insignificant results were obtained on self-esteem. Therefore, hypothesis 6 is accepted with 2 out of 3 variables.

Experience in sport-wise differences in term of Sports Participation and Self-confidence

Experience in Sport-wise Differences

Variables	Sports Experience	N	Mean	Std.	T	Df	Sig
Sport Participation	1-5 Years	171	2.5754	.36544	-.968	224	.180
	6 and above Years	55	2.6311	.38918			
Variables							
Self Confidence	1-5 Years	171	2.5848	.38256	-.954	224	.609
	6 and above Years	55	2.6418	.39473			

An Independent sample t-Test was applied to check the differences between individuals having experience in sports of 1-5 years and 6 and above years. The table shows that the test produced insignificant results for the mean differences between the two groups on sports participation, self-confidence, and self-esteem. Therefore, hypothesis 7 is rejected.

Relationship between sports participation and athletes' self-confidence

		Sports Participation	Self-Confidence
Sports participation	Pearson Correlation	1	.930**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	226	226
Self-confidence	Pearson Correlation	.930**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	226	226

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table shows the relationship between sports participation and self-confidence "R" (the value of correlation) and "P" (significant values) in respect of variables included in correlation analysis. The value of association between sports participation and self-confidence ($r = .930^{**}$ & $P = .000$).

Conclusion

According to the current study's findings, the sport has played an essential role in developing self-confidence in student-athletes at the university level. This may be achieved due to their colleges' sporting environments for student-athletes. This finding is linked with the results of Bowker (2006), whose study indicated a direct link between sports participation and self-confidence. Another study revealed a strong link between sport, peer acceptance and sport self-concept. Furthermore, sports participation positively predicts self-esteem (Chen et al., 2012). In line with this finding, Athanasius (2009) addressed in his study that confidence and sports have a great relationship. Sports develop self-confidence, while self-confidence evolves through sports. The author further stated that sports promote different social traits among their participants. So these findings are also in line with the present study (Lianopoulos et al., 2020). Developing psychological skills such as self-confidence and self-esteem is imperative for individuals, especially students. Within the youth sports literature, a large amount of research, including coaches, parents, and participants, has demonstrated life skills improvement through athletics among young people (Holt et al., 2017). In addition, research has repeatedly shown that coaches use a variety of tactics to help athletes acquire life skills (Pierce, Gould & Camiré, 2017).

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